

Molar Volumes of Cadmium Bromide and Cadmium Iodide in Aqueous Ethyleneglycol

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The molar volumes of cadmium bromide and cadmium iodide in aqueous ethyleneglycol (10, 20, 30 and 40%, w/w) are reported in the temperature range 30–45°. The limiting apparent molar volume is determined from Masson equation. The value of ϕ_v^∞ increases with the increase in temperature showing thereby that these salts behave as structure-makers in aqueous ethyleneglycol. Ion-solvent interaction decreases in case of bromide ions and increases in case of iodide ions with the increase in ethyleneglycol content. The temperature effect suggests that at 30% ethyleneglycol, bromide ions are more solvated than iodide ions.

ETHYLENEGLYCOL-water mixture behaves like an elastomer and its study has attracted attention due to its glassy behaviour. In the literature, extensive data^{1,2} have been accumulated on the study of 1:1 electrolytes in aqueous ethyleneglycol. Survey of literature shows no study regarding 2:1 electrolytes in aqueous ethyleneglycol. The purpose of the present communication is (i) to report data for cadmium bromide and cadmium iodide in aqueous ethyleneglycol at different temperatures and concentration, and (ii) to discuss ϕ_v^∞ and its dependence on temperature from the viewpoint of structure-breaking/-making capacity of the electrolyte from $\delta^2\phi_v^\infty/\delta t^2$.

Experimental

Cadmium halides were of AnalaR grade. Water of specific conductance of the order $10^{-6} \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ was used for making (by weight) the aqueous mixtures of ethyleneglycol. Density was measured with the help of the apparatus similar to the one designed by Ward and Millero³. A difference in weight of the float in water and ethyleneglycol at 30° was $\pm 6.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{g}$ and it gave a good precision in the measurement of density.

Results and Discussion

The apparent molar volumes (ϕ_v) for different solutions were calculated from equation⁴ (1),

$$\phi_v = 1000(d^0 - d)/mdd^0 + \frac{M_2}{d} \quad (1)$$

where, m is the molality and M_2 the molecular weight of the solute. The values of ϕ_v at different concentrations, temperatures and compositions of aqueous ethyleneglycol are given in Table 1. Errors arising from the determination of solution concentrations are generally not the limiting factor when

calculating the error in the apparent molar volumes. Consequently, errors in ϕ_v were calculated from equation (2) which assumes the error to be associated only with the density values of the solution and solvents⁵,

$$\Delta\phi_v = (2\Delta d/d^2)(1000/m + M_2) \quad (2)$$

Errors derived from this relation range from $\pm 0.01 \text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$ at 0.01 M to $\pm 0.15 \text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$ at 0.08 M .

TABLE 1—DENSITY AND APPARENT MOLAR VOLUMES OF CADMIUM BROMIDE AND IODIDE SOLUTION AT VARIOUS TEMPERATURES AND COMPOSITIONS OF AQUEOUS ETHYLENEGLYCOL

C $\times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$	Density g cm^{-3}	ϕ_v $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$
Cadmium bromide		
10% Ethyleneglycol, 30°, $d^0 = 1.00659$		
1.01	1.00940	64.01 ± 0.01
2.01	1.01207	70.96 ± 0.03
3.01	1.01474	73.14 ± 0.04
5.01	1.01994	77.46 ± 0.10
7.00	1.07514	79.08 ± 0.12
20% Ethyleneglycol, 30°, $d^0 = 1.02275$		
2.04	1.02882	46.62 ± 0.03
3.06	1.03170	51.01 ± 0.04
4.00	1.03444	56.58 ± 0.10
5.09	1.03719	59.83 ± 0.12
6.11	1.03986	63.07 ± 0.13
7.12	1.04253	65.92 ± 0.15
30% Ethyleneglycol, 30°, $d^0 = 1.03500$		
2.07	1.04104	51.52 ± 0.03
3.10	1.04390	55.20 ± 0.04
4.13	1.04678	56.85 ± 0.06
5.15	1.04960	59.16 ± 0.10
7.21	1.05508	63.51 ± 0.11
8.23	1.05783	64.81 ± 0.12
40% Ethyleneglycol, 30°, $d^0 = 1.04982$		
3.13	1.05602	139.41 ± 0.03
4.17	1.05862	128.83 ± 0.04
5.21	1.06136	117.13 ± 0.05
6.25	1.06396	112.53 ± 0.10
7.29	1.06656	109.19 ± 0.11
8.32	1.06916	106.63 ± 0.12

(Table 1 contd.)

 30% Ethyleneglycol, 35°, $d^{\circ}=1.038\ 29$

2.06	1.039 21	49.96 ± 0.03
3.09	1.042 17	59.60 ± 0.03
4.12	1.044 98	56.55 ± 0.10
5.15	1.047 79	58.88 ± 0.11
7.20	1.053 42	61.28 ± 0.12
8.22	1.056 24	61.98 ± 0.13

 30% Ethyleneglycol, 45°, $d^{\circ}=1.028\ 74$

2.05	1.038 87	92.11 ± 0.02
3.08	1.036 39	93.01 ± 0.04
4.10	1.038 85	95.06 ± 0.05
5.12	1.041 30	96.18 ± 0.08
7.15	1.046 06	99.20 ± 0.05
8.16	1.048 44	100.04 ± 0.011

Cadmium iodide

 10% Ethyleneglycol, 30°, $d^{\circ}=1.006\ 59$

2.01	1.012 94	50.09 ± 0.03
3.01	1.016 04	52.30 ± 0.04
4.02	1.019 00	56.86 ± 0.05
5.01	1.021 96	59.85 ± 0.08
7.02	1.028 02	60.33 ± 0.10
8.01	1.031 05	60.53 ± 0.12

 20% Ethyleneglycol, 30°, $d^{\circ}=1.022\ 75$

2.04	1.025 71	215.99 ± 0.01
3.05	1.028 53	173.10 ± 0.02
4.07	1.031 34	151.56 ± 0.04
5.08	1.034 16	138.53 ± 0.05
7.10	1.039 78	123.41 ± 0.10
8.10	1.042 60	118.61 ± 0.11

 30% Ethyleneglycol, 30°, $d^{\circ}=1.035\ 00$

2.06	1.039 14	159.93 ± 0.02
3.09	1.041 88	138.31 ± 0.03
4.12	1.044 62	128.01 ± 0.04
5.14	1.047 22	124.16 ± 0.10
6.16	1.049 89	120.39 ± 0.11
7.18	1.052 41	119.52 ± 0.12

 40% Ethyleneglycol, 30°, $d^{\circ}=1\ 049\ 82$

2.01	1.054 72	125.79 ± 0.03
4.18	1.061 07	92.64 ± 0.05
5.28	1.064 82	84.41 ± 0.10
6.27	1.067 50	80.11 ± 0.11
8.34	1.073 85	74.57 ± 0.13
9.38	1.077 02	71.90 ± 0.14

 30% Ethyleneglycol, 40°, $d^{\circ}=1.030\ 91$

2.05	1.033 65	231.06 ± 0.01
3.08	1.036 32	184.51 ± 0.02
4.10	1.038 85	167.21 ± 0.04
5.11	1.041 37	157.72 ± 0.05
6.13	1.043 90	149.63 ± 0.10
8.15	1.048 95	140.47 ± 0.12

 30% Ethyleneglycol, 45°, $d^{\circ}=1.028\ 74$

2.05	1.031 63	218.91 ± 0.01
3.10	1.034 37	177.77 ± 0.02
4.09	1.037 11	156.93 ± 0.04
5.11	1.039 86	144.38 ± 0.05
6.12	1.042 60	135.93 ± 0.10
7.13	1.045 27	130.79 ± 0.12

It has been found that the density of various solutions can be represented by Root equation⁶,

$$d = d^{\circ} + AC - BC^{3/2} \quad (3)$$

where, d° is density of the solvent, C the concentration, and A and B are the constants of Root equation. On plotting $(d - d^{\circ})/C$ vs $\sqrt{C}$, a straight line was obtained in each case as expected. The

values of A and B evaluated from the intercept and the slope of the plots are given in Tables 2 and 3.

 TABLE 2—VALUES OF A AND B OF ROOT EQUATION FOR CADMIUM BROMIDE AND CADMIUM IODIDE IN DIFFERENT COMPOSITIONS OF AQUEOUS ETHYLENEGGLYCOL AT 30°

Solvent system	A	B
Cadmium bromide		
10% Ethyleneglycol	0.282	0.133
20% Ethyleneglycol	0.321	0.400
30% Ethyleneglycol	0.311	0.402
40% Ethyleneglycol	0.189	0.150
Cadmium iodide		
10% Ethyleneglycol	0.330	0.157
20% Ethyleneglycol	0.665	0.783
30% Ethyleneglycol	0.176	0.500
40% Ethyleneglycol	0.244	0.181

 TABLE 3—VALUES OF A AND B OF ROOT EQUATION FOR CADMIUM BROMIDE AND CADMIUM IODIDE AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES IN 30% ETHYLENEGGLYCOL

Solvent system	Temp. °C	A	B
Cadmium bromide			
30% Ethyleneglycol	30	0.304	0.157
	35	0.302	0.105
	45	0.258	0.083
Cadmium iodide			
30% Ethyleneglycol	30	0.132	0.250
	40	0.900	0.600
	45	0.976	0.555

The apparent molar volume data can be represented by the Masson equation⁷,

$$\phi_v = \phi_v^{\circ} + S_v \sqrt{C} \quad (4)$$

where, ϕ_v° is the limiting apparent molar volume and S_v the experimental slope. ϕ_v° has been interpreted as a measure of solute-solvent interactions and S_v the measure of ion-ion interaction. The limiting values of ϕ_v° estimated from the Masson plots are given in Tables 4 and 5.

 TABLE 4—VALUES OF ϕ_v° FOR CADMIUM BROMIDE AND CADMIUM IODIDE IN DIFFERENT COMPOSITIONS OF ETHYLENEGGLYCOL AT 30°

Solvent system	Temp. °C	ϕ_v° (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)
Cadmium bromide		
10% Ethyleneglycol	30	57.90 ± 1.85
20% Ethyleneglycol		29.35 ± 1.50
30% Ethyleneglycol		39.01 ± 1.30
40% Ethyleneglycol		193.25 ± 1.00
Cadmium iodide		
10% Ethyleneglycol	30	40.00 ± 1.40
20% Ethyleneglycol		290.00 ± 1.25
30% Ethyleneglycol		164.90 ± 1.30
40% Ethyleneglycol		182.80 ± 0.05

TABLE 5—VALUES OF ϕ_v° FOR CADMIUM BROMIDE AND CADMIUM IODIDE AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES IN 30% ETHYLENEGLYCOL

Temp. °C	ϕ_v° (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)
Cadmium bromide	
30	39.01 ± 1.30
35	39.55 ± 1.25
45	82.25 ± 1.00
Cadmium iodide	
30	164.90 ± 1.30
40	259.00 ± 1.00
45	274.7 ± 0.55

ϕ_v° is a measure of solute-solvent interactions⁸ and from the values of ϕ_v° at different compositions of aqueous ethyleneglycol it is found that solute-solute interaction is opposite in both the salts. In case of cadmium bromide, it decreases at lower composition and increases after 30% aqueous ethyleneglycol, while in case of cadmium iodide it increases first and decreases after 30% aqueous ethyleneglycol. Since cation is common in both the cases it can be concluded that bromide ion-ethyleneglycol interaction increases and the iodide ion-ethyleneglycol interaction decreases at higher composition (>10%) of ethyleneglycol.

The temperature dependence of ϕ_v° in 30% (w/w) ethyleneglycol can be represented by the following equation in the range 30–45°,

For cadmium bromide :

$$\phi_v^\circ (\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}) = 12.00 - 0.09t + 0.054t^2 \quad (\text{A})$$

For cadmium iodide :

$$\phi_v^\circ (\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}) = 101.90 + 2.4t - 0.01t^2 \quad (\text{B})$$

where, t is the temperature (°C). It has been pointed out earlier that variation in ϕ_v° with temperature can be interpreted in terms of solvation of ions. Accordingly, the increase in ϕ_v° of CdBr₂ with increasing temperature and decrease in ϕ_v° of CdI₂ with increasing temperature suggest that bromide ions are more solvated than the iodide ions. It is further found that $\delta^2\phi_v^\circ/\delta t^2$ is positive in case of cadmium bromide showing thereby that it is structure-maker and negative in case of cadmium iodide showing thereby that it is structure breaker¹⁰.

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